

CHARACTERISTICS OF THE FIELD OF PHYSICAL CULTURE

Begaliyev Bakhtiyor Atavulloyevich

Karshi State University, Senior teacher of the Department of Physical Education and Sports

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Abstract. *This article discusses the specific aspects, goals and objectives, tools and methods of the field of physical culture. How important this field is in our society has been described in detail.*

Keywords: *physical culture, principle, method, sport, society, skill, skill, boxing, judo, freestyle wrestling, rhythmic gymnastics, weightlifting, chess.*

INTRODUCTION

The years of independence are literally spent with the implementation of large-scale reforms aimed at determining the perspective of the socio-economic and cultural development of the Republic of Uzbekistan, striving to take a worthy place among the countries of the world community. Studying the experiences of the developed countries of the world, taking into account local conditions, economic and intellectual resources, the implementation of fundamental reforms in all spheres of society ensures new achievements [1]. The sphere of physical culture and sports occupies the most important place in the socio-economic and cultural development of our people. Physical culture and sports as a social sphere educate people to be physically, mentally and spiritually mature and perfect individuals, and economically, they are productive entities, i.e. by restoring and strengthening the health and high working abilities of people, the production and economy of our country develops. contributes. As we know from history, the field of physical education and sports in every society serves the ideology of this society and develops under the influence of the ideology of this society. From the first days of independence, our state paid great attention to physical education and sports as the main factor in raising a mature generation, and it became one of the priority directions of state policy, and even today, great reforms are being carried out by our state.

The emergence of physical education refers to the oldest periods in the history of human society. Elements of physical education were created in primitive society. People got their own food, hunted, built houses, and during this natural, necessary activity, their physical abilities - strength, endurance, speed - developed by themselves.

Gradually, during the historical process, people noticed that the representatives of the tribe, who lead a more active and mobile lifestyle, repeatedly repeat certain physical actions, and show physical strength, are stronger, more durable and more efficient. This led to people's conscious understanding of the phenomenon of exercise (repetition of movements) in Asian countries. During the Middle Ages, ancient physical culture practices became widespread in India. Wrestling, archery, running, horse games were used in this. Along with national dances, khatkha-yog (Indian gymnastics), i.e., body movement standards, ritual (ritual) games, etc. became popular [3].

During the last years, athletes of our country won more than a thousand medals in various international competitions, more than 400 of them are gold medals. Currently, the schools established in Uzbekistan for boxing, judo, freestyle wrestling, rhythmic gymnastics, weightlifting, chess and other sports are known and famous all over the world.

Today, the development of physical education and sports among the population, especially the role of sports in the education of young people, is being given great importance, and a number of practical works have been started in this regard.

Today, young people make up an unprecedented majority of the world's population, i.e. more than 2 billion people. In this regard, the fact that young people between the ages of 15 and 25 make up nearly 50 percent of the world's population is of great importance. In Uzbekistan alone, more than 60 percent of the population are young people under the age of 35. The future of any country is definitely built by the youth.

The COVID-19 infection, which has not lost its influence even today, shows how important the role of physical education and sports is in establishing a healthy lifestyle of people and increasing personal immunity put to date: "659,675,056 people worldwide have been infected with Covid, of which 6,678,336 have died. In our country, this indicator is 249,045 people infected with Covid, and 1,637 of them died."

It was noted that immunity is the most necessary thing for the human body in the face of such a huge disaster that has befallen the entire humanity. People with strong immunity survived this disease mildly, but people with the opposite were not helped by medicine. A strong immunity can be achieved through a healthy lifestyle, the consumption of useful and high-quality food products, and most importantly, continuous and systematic physical training.

The main way to create a healthy lifestyle and prevent various diseases is a properly organized culture of physical activity, sports, and a health care system. Physical activity normalizes the work of organs and systems in the entire human body, helps restore impaired physiological functions, increases mental and physical activity.

Physical education is an integral part of general education aimed at strengthening health and harmonious development of the human body. One of the indicators of physical culture in society.

The daily development of physical education and sports in Uzbekistan is pleasing to all of us. The incomparable importance of sports in forming a physically fit person is reflected in the decisions made by our government in recent years. This is the truth. Because it is no exaggeration to say that physical education and sports are the key to improving the health of the population and maintaining human health. We have been witnessing the confirmation of the sentence "Nothing can quickly introduce a country to the world like sports."

Physical culture occupies a deep place in the general culture of the peoples of the world. Its teaching, learning and scientific research is one of the urgent problems of today [2].

The first traces and examples of physical culture are more common in the states around the Mediterranean Sea (Mesopotamia) that emerged in the IV century BC. The content and forms of physical exercise are expressed in military activities. Activities such as archery, hand-to-hand combat, boxing, chariot racing, and archery play an important role in this.

Only if physical culture relies on a specific system, the intended result will be achieved. The system of physical culture means, first of all, the generality of principles, tools, methods of physical culture and the forms of its organization, which are compatible with the goals and tasks of harmonious development of a member of society in all aspects.

The issue of the defense of our homeland also imposes a number of requirements on the physical culture process established in our society, and as a result of the implementation of these requirements, the objective characteristics of the physical culture system are manifested. The all-

round physical fitness and well-developed physical qualities of the population of our country should serve as an indicator of readiness for the defense of the Motherland.

LITERATURE ANALYSIS AND METHODOLOGY

Therefore, one of the main goals of physical culture in Uzbekistan is to educate the people of Uzbekistan who have reached physical maturity, are active builders of the legal state, and are ready for creative work and defense of the Motherland. This goal is common to all organizations and institutions implementing physical culture in the country.

The generality of the goal is one of the main laws of the physical culture system. In response to the specified goals and conditions, the age, health, physical fitness, and profession of the participants are taken into account in its implementation, and specific tasks in physical culture are solved. General tasks are assigned to the physical culture system, which are as follows:

a) giving direction to the harmonious development of the form and function of the human organism, the all-round improvement of physical abilities, strengthening of health and ensuring the longevity of the people;

b) formation of necessary life skills and abilities, special knowledge of physical culture needed in everyday life;

c) culturalization of physical qualities for comprehensive development;

The purpose and task of human physical culture, its connection with other cultural processes is understood to be compatible only if this compatibility is objective in nature and gives a legal direction to the process of physical culture. It has been proven in practice that goal-oriented activities in the process of physical culture, like in other areas of culture, cannot always correspond to the planned result. In physical culture, the result of culture is the planned physical in the training of a young athlete or a physical culturist it is important to consider how exercise affects the body: If we pay attention to the results of short-term sports training, we will see that the achievement of high results is within a certain period, and if the previous ones are forgotten, the training will not pay off later. This allows for all-round harmonious development and destroys sports achievements. That's why the requirement of far-sightedness is a priority for pedagogues and trainers. Solving this task requires the training of well-educated specialists who know and love their work. And these specialists are able to positively solve the goals and tasks that should be realized in the physical culture system of the country, it is necessary to educate the young generation to be physically healthy and mentally mature from childhood. Navqiran, just recognition of our identity At the initiative of state and non-state sports societies of different categories of our country, as well as associations of physical culture enthusiasts, increasing attention to the creation of a unified system of physical culture, it embodies the following main features: spiritual perfection and scientificity.

Eastern thinkers have always paid special attention to the issue of a spiritually mature and perfect person. It is said that the greatest quality of perfection lies in the perfection of the human body. Human fortitude, religion, discipline, contentment, knowledge, patience, discipline, desire, conscience, truthfulness, theoretical lesson, chastity, modesty, understanding, intelligence, economy, obedience, benevolence, morality, loyalty, justice, love, high diligence, forgiveness, positive qualities such as love of the country (A. Avloni. "Turkish flower garden or morals" Tashkent "teacher" 1992. page 13) were considered to be achieved only through a healthy body and spirituality.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

We are national when we mean the nationalism of the physical culture system of our country physical exercises that are common among the masses in the form of games. national sport There are a lot of types, mass sports, "big sports" included in the Olympic program it is understood that there is an opportunity to engage the peoples of our national republic.

The scientific nature of the concept of physical culture can be seen in the fact that the wide spread of scientific research in the field of physical culture and its connection with practice, pedagogy, psychology, anatomy, physiology, biomechanics, sports metrology, sports medicine, treatment of physical culture, where the theory and practice of physical culture are considered scientific disciplines based on the fact that their scientific achievements are aimed at meeting the vital needs of our people.

CONCLUSION

The system of physical culture is related to groups divided, and even now, implementation of various programs of the cultural process is carried out in these groups:

- a) preschool education (state and non-state preschool institutions) group;
- b) group of physical culture of school-aged children (grades I-IX of general secondary education);
- c) group of secondary special, vocational education (academic lyceums, vocational schools);
- g) higher education group;
- d) army group;

The physical culture system combines the following main elements:

- a) the goal, objectives and principles of physical culture compatibility;
- b) tools used in the physical culture system - physical exercises such as gymnastics, games, sports, tourism, etc.;

It is worth noting that physical culture in developed countries the use of various systems of the field is not limited.

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